

BDAIM-2025

PROCEEDINGS

of the International Scientific and Practical Conference

Big Data and Artificial Intelligence in Modeling
International Socio-Economic Processes

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

May 27, 2025

University of World Economy and Diplomacy
Moscow State Institute of International Relations
National University of Uzbekistan

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Big Data & AI for Global Socio-
Economic Modeling

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Big Data and Artificial Intelligence
in Modeling

International Socio-Economic Processes

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(Conference Proceedings)

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International Scientific and Practical Conference – BDAIM-2025

Big Data and Artificial Intelligence in Modeling International Socio-Economic Processes

The **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**, in collaboration with **MGIMO University** and the **National University of Uzbekistan (NUUz)**, hosted the international scientific and practical conference **BDAIM-2025** on **May 27, 2025** in **Tashkent, Uzbekistan**.

The main **goal** of the conference was to unite researchers, policy makers, experts, and educators to explore cutting-edge applications of **big data** and **artificial intelligence (AI)** in modeling **international socio-economic processes**. Particular emphasis was placed on interdisciplinary approaches and digital transformation in economics, governance, and education.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **Theoretical Foundations:** big data processing, machine learning algorithms, interpretability.
- **Socio-Economic Modeling:** global trade, finance, migration, and digital economies.
- **Global Challenges:** AI for climate change, pandemics, geopolitical risk management.
- **International Relations:** digital diplomacy, media analytics, conflict forecasting.
- **Ethics and Regulation:** AI governance, data protection, algorithmic responsibility.
- **Mathematical Models:** econometrics, game theory, uncertainty and risk analysis.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Sug'urta faoliyatining iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlari tendensiyalarining panel regression modellari

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Sug'urta faoliyatining iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlari tendensiyalarining panel retrospektiv (statistik) ma'lumotlari asosida adekvat modellarni aniqlash orqali istiqboldagi rejalarini belgilash va sohada olib borilayotgan ishlar natijalarini kuzatish imkoniyati yaratiladi.

Tahlillarimizda 2019-2023 yillar bo'yicha 13 ta hududlar kesimida asosiy qishloq xo'jaligi ekinlari bo'yicha sug'urta faoliyati panel ma'lumotlarlari gravitatsion panel modellari yordamida tahlil qilingan.

Panel ma'lumotlardagi geterogenlikni qanday modellashtirishga ko'ra, quyidagi model turlari mavjud:

(i) umumiy effekt modeli (*ing.* Common Effect Model - CEM).

Umumiy effekt modelida turli birliklar bo'yicha ma'lumotlar individual farqlar bo'yicha hech qanday taxminlarsiz birlashtiriladi:

$$y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{1it} + \dots + \beta_k x_{kit} + u_{it}$$

bu yerda y_{it} — bog'liq o'zgaruvchi; x_{kit} — k -mustaqil o'zgaruvchi; u_{it} — xatolik; β_0 — kesishma; β_1, \dots, β_k — struktura parametrlar.

Bunda quyidagi farazlar o'rinli:

$$\begin{aligned} E(u) &= 0 \\ E(uu') &= \sigma_u^2 I \\ \text{rank}(X) &= K + 1 < NT \\ E(u|X) &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

(ii) sobit effekt modeli (*ing.* Fixed Effect Model - FEM).

Modelda

$$y_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 x_{1it} + \dots + \beta_k x_{kit} + u_{it}$$

individual *kesishmalar* (α_i) individual va vaqt o'zgarmas xususiyatlarini nazorat qilish uchun kiritiladi. *Ushbu kesishmalar sobit effektlar* deb ataladi. Ruqsat etilgan effektlar individual *geterogenlikni* qamrab oladi.

$$\text{cov}(u_{i,t}, u_{i,s}) \neq 0$$

(iii) tasodifiy effekt modeli (*ing.* Random Effect Model - REM).

$$y_{it} = \alpha + X_i' \beta + u_{it}, \quad i \in \{1, \dots, N\}, \quad t \in \{1, \dots, T\}.$$

Xatolik komponenti (u_{it}) individual *tasodifiy komponent* (μ_i) va *idiosinkratik farqlar* (ε_{it}) yig'indisidir:

$$u_{it} = \mu_i + \varepsilon_{it}, \quad \mu_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_\mu^2), \quad \varepsilon_{it} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2).$$

Tadqiqotimizda qishloq xo'jaligi ekinlari bo'yicha sug'urta faoliyati ma'lumotlari asosida ushbu shakllantirilgan bo'lib, ulardan qishloq xo'jaligi ekinlari bo'yicha sug'urta faoliyatini baholash uchun eng munosib modelni aniqlash uchun ushbu ba'zi muntazam testlar o'tkaziladi: Chou testi, Hausman testi va Lagrange Multiplier (LM) testi.

Chou testi model tanlashda foydalidir va umumiy effekt hamda sobit effekt modellari o'rtasida qaror qabul qilish imkonini beradi (Helpman et al., 2008). Hausman testi regressiya xatoliklari bilan mustaqil o'zgaruvchilar o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni tekshiradi va REM hamda FEM o'rtasidagi eng mos modelni aniqlashga yordam beradi (Baldwin & Taglioni, 2006). LM testi esa umumiy va tasodifiy effekt modellarini taqqoslaydi.

Dastlab, bog'liq o'zgaruvchi sifatida tanlangan sug'urta shartnomalari soni uchun ma'lumotlar asosida aniqlaganimiz barcha panel gravitasion modellarni keltirib o'tamiz.

1-jadval. Qishloq xo'jaligi ekinlari bo'yicha sug'urta shartnomalari sonining panel

Ko'rsatkichlar	1-model (CEM)	2- model (FEM)	3- model (REM)
R ²	0.95	0.97	0.95
Adj R ²	0.94	0.92	0.94
Regressiyaning standart xatoligi	0.499	0.559	0.499
Darbin Uotson	2.718	3.659	2.718
Model xulosasi	Fisher F-statistikasi: 95.220 p-qiyamati: 0.000	Fisher F-statistikasi: 22.792 p-qiyamati: 0.000	Fisher F-statistikasi: 95.220 p-qiyamati: 0.000

*Izoh: Qavs Ichida standart xatolik keltirilgan. Ahamiyatlilik darajasi.: *** 0.01, **0.05; * 0.10.*

Barcha o'zgaruvchiular logarifmlarda berilgan.

1-Jadvaldagi Qishloq xo'jaligi ekinlari bo'yicha sug'urta shartnomalari sonining panel gravitasion modellar natijalaridan ko'rinadiki, umumiy effekt modeli (CEM), sobit effekt modeli(FEM) va tasodifiy effekt model (REM) lari Fisher F-statistikasiga ko'ra ahamiyatli modellar sifatida baholangan. Qurilishi jihatdan umumiy effekt (CEM) va tasodifiy effekt (REM) modellari o'xshash bo'lib, Regressiyaning standart xatoligi kamligi jihatdan FEM modelidan ustunroqdir, FEM modeli esa bu modellardan farq qiladi. O'zgaruvchilarning nisbatan ko'p qamroviga va yuqori ahamiyatlilik daragasiga ko'ra, CEM va REM modellari REM dan ko'ra yaxshiroq deb xulosa qilish mumkin. Modellar ichidan eng yaxshisini aniqlash uchun tahlillarni ishonchligini ta'minlash maqsadida, modellarni solishtiruvchi gepotezalar tahlillarini amalga oshiramiz.

Dastlab, CEM va FEM o'rtasida panel ma'lumotlarini baholash modelini tanlash uchun gepotezalar yordamida ehtimollik Chou testini amalga oshiramiz:

2-jadval. Chou testi (Likelihood Test) natijalari

Ko'rsatkichlar	1-model (CEM)	2- model (FEM)	3- model (REM)
R ²	0.95	0.97	0.95
Adj R ²	0.94	0.92	0.94
Regressiyaning standart xatoligi	0.499	0.559	0.499
Darbin Uotson	2.718	3.659	2.718
Model xulosasi	Fisher F-statistikasi: 95.220 p-qiymati: 0.000	Fisher F-statistikasi: 22.792 p-qiymati: 0.000	Fisher F-statistikasi: 95.220 p-qiymati: 0.000

Izoh: Qavs Ichida standart xatolik keltirilgan. Ahamiyatlilik darajasi.: *** 0.01, **0.05,* 0.10.

Barcha o'zgaruvchiular logarifmlarda berilgan.

2-jadvaldagi ehtimollik-test natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, Chi-kvadratning ehtimollik qiymati 0.346 ni tashkil qiladi va u ehtimollik qiymati 0,05 dan katta ($\chi^2 = 0.346 > p = 0.005$). Test natijalariga asoslanib xulosa qilish mumkinki, ikkala modeldan eng yaxshi panel ma'lumotlarini baholash modeli CEM hisoblanadi.

Keyingi bosqichda Hausman testi yordamida FEM va REM o'rtasida taqqoslashini bajaramiz. Hausman testi FEM va REM o'rtasidagi eng yaxshi modelni aniqlash uchun amalga oshiriladi. (3-jadval).

3-jadval. Chou testi (Likelihood Test) natijalar Hausman testi natijalari

Test	Statistika	Erkinlik darajasi	Ehtimolligi
F-test	0.582	(12,13)	0.822
χ^2 (Xi-kvadrat)	13.322	12	0.346
Gepotezaning qo'yilishi: H ₀ : CEM afzalroq H ₁ : FEM afzalroq		Qaror qabul qilish: Agar Chi-kvadratning ehtimollik qiymati > 0,05 bo'lsa, H ₀ qabul qilinadi. Agar Chi-kvadratning ehtimollik qiymati < 0,05 bo'lsa, H ₀ rad etiladi.	

Jadvaldagi Hausman testi natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, tasodifiy kesishmaning ehtimollik qiymati > 0,05 ekanligi tasodifiy effekt modeli REM ning sobit effekt modeli FEM dan yaxshiroq ekanligini anglatadi. Diagnostik baholashlarga asoslanib, o'z navbatida, Chou testidan aniqlangan CEM va Hausman testi natijalaridan aniqlangan REM modellarini solishtirish uchun Lagranj multiplikatori (LM) test sinovlarini amalga oshiramiz.

4-jadval. Lagranj multiplikatori (LM) testi natijalari

Ko'rsatkichlar	1-model (CEM)	2- model (FEM)	3- model (REM)
R ²	0.95	0.97	0.95
Adj R ²	0.94	0.92	0.94
Regressiyaning standart xatoligi	0.499	0.559	0.499
Darbin Uotson	2.718	3.659	2.718
Model xulosasi	Fisher F-statistikasi: 95.220 p-qiymati: 0.000	Fisher F- statistikasi: 22.792 p-qiymati: 0.000	Fisher F-statistikasi: 95.220 p-qiymati: 0.000

*Izoh: Qavs Ichida standart xatolik keltirilgan. Ahamiyatlilik darajasi.: *** 0.01, **0.05,* 0.10.*

Barcha o'zgaruvchiular logarifmlarda berilgan.

Lagranj multiplikatori (LM)testi natijalariga ko'ra $p=0.0969 > 0.05$ ekanligidan xulosa qilishimiz mumkinki, qishloq xo'jaligi ekinlari bo'yicha sug'urta shartnomalari sonini eng yaxshi ifodalaydigan panel gravitasion model sifatida umumiy effekt CEM modeli ekanligi aniqlandi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

1. Anderson, J. E. (1979). A theoretical foundation for the gravity equation. *American Economic Review*, 69(1), 106-116.
2. Baldwin, R., & Taglioni, D. (2006). Gravity for dummies and dummies for gravity equations. National Bureau of Economic Research Working Paper No. 12516.
3. CEPII (2023). Geographical and institutional datasets. Retrieved from <https://www.cepii.fr>.
4. Helpman, E., Melitz, M., & Rubinstein, Y. (2008). Estimating trade flows: Trading partners and trading volumes. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 123(2), 441-487.
5. Kim, S. (2022). Immigration flows and international trade: A gravity model approach. *Journal of International Economics*, 137, 103612.
6. LeSage, J. P., & Pace, R. K. (2009). *Introduction to spatial econometrics*. Boca Raton: CRC Press.